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FULLER APPROACH ON KEY STAGES 1 READING PERFORMANCE

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1. INTRODUCTION

The Fuller Approach offers resources to support reading instruction. It is a teaching methodology focusing on reading performance and critical thinking. Among the salient themes of this approach are emphasizing comprehension of the material, utilizing graded texts, and integrating reading and writing. It also highlights several advantages, including improved reading performance, differentiation in learning, the development of critical thinking skills, and increased motivation among students.

The Fuller Approach comprises systematic instructional materials that educators can use when teaching reading. It includes sound-it-out lessons on letters, words, phrases, sentences, reading fairy tales, and picture-matching activities. The more comprehensive technique courses employ a spiral method of teaching reading, where each lesson focuses on a particular sound, word, phrase, sentence, or story. Fulfilling children's reading performance is essential for success in school. It also integrates phonics and the sounds of the alphabet into its word recognition teaching method (Eghbaria et al., 2022).

Before using this approach, learners must be able to recall the names and sounds of the alphabet. Once familiar with the letters, they begin decoding sounds by combining letters to form words and introducing word families with the same ending sounds. Moreover, another goal of this method is to enhance reading and vocabulary achievement. As a result, the worth and value of reading material are enhanced. This method is based on systematic and explicit classroom instruction, gradually guiding young children through carefully planned lessons that introduce new sounds, words, and skills in a structured and explicit manner. These strategies help children develop phonemic awareness, which significantly improves the instruction process for word recognition.

In the shifting global educational landscape, researchers have analyzed the process of reading acquisition skills, and to date, it remains an international area of interest and difficulty. Reading is one of the most essential macro skills in English that students should master. It is a fundamental function today and a prerequisite for learning.

Reading performance is a core aspect of literacy that determines the ability to read, interpret, and analyze written texts. It is a direct force behind academic performance and overall intellectual growth. Strong reading performance enhances comprehension, communication, and critical thinking, while poor reading performance can hinder learning progress and limit future opportunities.

The ability to read is essential for understanding the world around us as well as ourselves. Without reading skills, life can be challenging to navigate. Today's young children's future is dependent on their ability to comprehend and carefully apply a wide range of texts. It also depends on their ability to employ reading abilities to think critically and articulate their thoughts and opinions both orally and in writing. (Department of Education, 2013).

Reading is a foundational skill that everyone should be able to perform. It is helpful in many ways, for instance, reading signage, traveling on public transportation, reading labels on groceries, purchasing goods, and many more. It is also essential during the foundational years of a child, when it should be developed at a young age. Chin and Hashim (2022) believe that reading is a complicated skill that primary learners should be able to learn at an early age. It is an essential tool that one should

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possess to become successful. Many efforts are required to help pupils develop the habit of reading, understand the meaning of the text, and enjoy reading because it is a significant requirement for them (Fergina et al., 2024).

In today's environment, reading performance is critical for success. It measures a person's ability to understand and reflect on written content. The Program for International Students Assessment (PISA) is a standardized assessment that assesses three significant domains, one of which is reading. According to the recent 2022 PISA results, the Philippines had a low ranking in reading among participating countries, ranking 77 out of 81 (OECD, 2023).

The primary purpose of reading is to determine the meaning or message of a given text. Teaching young children to read early helps develop their language skills and reading performance, which are complex skills required for ongoing development. Foundational literacy skills should be mastered at a young age; the inability to do so significantly reduces the chances of effective teaching. Moreover, according to Crawford et al. (2024), if a child is not taught to read in primary school, they will struggle to advance to higher levels of education. Berdera et al. (2021) emphasize that the early identification of at-risk students for reading failure is crucial for effective intervention placement. Most teachers believe that early identification and remediation of at-risk learners through intervention will help struggling readers using the Fuller Approach. Teachers believe that the most effective way to support at-risk readers is to provide targeted interventions tailored to their individual needs (Meramonte, 2022).

Developing children's reading readiness is the primary focus of early primary classroom instruction. When children fail to acquire effective reading strategies, teachers look for suitable interventions to help pupils improve their reading performance. Research has shown that most children dislike reading for various reasons, which negatively impacts their learning performance (Fergina et al., 2024). Low motivation and lack of good comprehension skills are the primary reasons (Fergina et al., 2024). According to Gevero and Doronio (2024), A more comprehensive strategy will be applied in the different grades, particularly for students at the initial level of learning. Early intervention can help younger students who struggle with reading, potentially preventing long-term academic difficulties.

Professional educators worldwide continually seek new and innovative ways to teach reading, recognizing the importance of this skill for students' academic success. For instance, the No Child Left Behind Act was passed at the national level in the United States. The No Child Left Behind Act resulted in the creation of a new program, Reading First. According to McKeown and Barnett (2007), this program provides financial support to help states and local education districts enhance reading comprehension instruction from kindergarten through grade 3. Reading First schools receive funding from the U.S. federal government. This funding is intended to help ensure that every student can read at or above grade level by the end of third grade (Duke & Block, 2012).

In Spain, researchers believe that letter-naming fluency is the best precursor to early reading experiences, and poor early reading performance in children is explained by deficits in phonological awareness, naming speed, and visual orientation. (De la Calle et al. (2020)).

Many cognitive processes involved in learning are linked to reading. Reading and writing are essential for introducing young people to humanity's collective knowledge and can have a profound impact on their lives. In the initial stage of development, referred to as readiness, young children cultivate foundational skills critical for later structured reading instruction. This stage is crucial, as it involves establishing phonemic awareness, vocabulary, and comprehension skills that are the foundation of subsequent literacy development. Furthermore, participating in activities that foster exposure and exploration, such as reading aloud, discussing, and working with books and other print materials, can significantly enhance the learning process. These activities not only evoke curiosity but

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also create a love for reading. Additionally, in most developing countries, there is a need to prioritize reading projects and educational programs so that they are made available and culturally relevant, rather than being neglected. Encouraging early literacy has the potential to close schooling gaps and enable children to thrive academically, and even more.

In Indonesia, initiatives such as the Merdeka Learning Program, Episode 23, titled "Good Quality Reading Books for Indonesian Literacy," have been launched to address the issue of low literacy skills in children, which is often attributed to a lack of habit formation at an early age. Minister of Education, Culture, Research, and Technology Nadiem Anwar Makarim emphasized that high-quality books could capture children's interest early, improving Indonesia's literacy rate (Jakarta Antara, 2023). The initiative aims to provide high-quality reading materials for students in Early Childhood Education (PAUD) and Elementary Schools (SD), along with teacher training programs. Using various techniques, Indonesian educators can enhance children's interest in reading and better meet their needs.

National studies highlight the importance of using various methods when teaching reading to young students. These approaches introduce children to new vocabulary and enhance their language skills.

In the Philippines, many researchers are conducting in-depth studies on the efficacy of the Fuller Approach, a methodology designed specifically for reading instruction. The approach focuses on developing literacy skills through interactive and systematic methods to enhance students' reading abilities.

These researchers seek to provide valuable insights into best practices for teaching reading in the country by analyzing its impact in diverse educational settings.

In Mindanao, specifically in the Donmar Lopez Copada Integrated Indigenous People's School, situated in the Maasim 3 District of Sarangani, Goyja (2023) discovered that the Fuller approach can significantly improve the reading skills of Grade 3 students. Those taught using this strategy showed substantial gains in reading fluency, accuracy, and comprehension. The Fuller technique can be an effective tool for educators seeking to enhance reading skills in primary students.

Similarly, improving reading skills effectively requires cooperation from parents or guardians. Teaching reading has always been challenging at Pagasa Malipayan in Agusan Del Sur. Several programs and initiatives have been launched to support teachers in finding alternative ways to help students understand concepts more clearly. According to the studies conducted, it was found that 25 out of 40 students in grades 3-6 read at a frustration level. It highlights the need for an intervention to strengthen their word-reading and reading comprehension skills, enabling them to remain engaged with their peers and participate fully in class discussions. (Gevero & Doronio, 2024). The researcher proposes applying the Fuller Approach to other grades, particularly to students beginning their education. Providing early assistance can help struggling young readers avoid long-term academic challenges. The Fuller Approach should continue and be further enhanced because it has considerably increased reading skills. The findings also indicate a significant increase in students' reading proficiency resulting from the implementation of the Fuller Approach. Thus, the study shows that using the Fuller Approach is recommended for improving students' reading ability and comprehension.

The research in Catbalogan City School Division's District VI was continued to determine the level of reading proficiency among Grade 3 students. Through the administration of various tests, it was established that most students found reading very challenging; thus, the rationale for a structured reading timetable. This type of schedule remains crucial in establishing a reading habit and enhancing performance among the respondents. The findings also provide evidence of the viability of developing a specific reading intervention program to address the needs of these students. The

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program could include interventions such as guided reading, phonics practice, and interactive reading to improve their reading skills and create a lifelong reading habit.

Meramonte (2022) emphasizes that early identification of students at risk for future reading failure is crucial for correctly placing them in intervention and remediation programs. However, after being selected and enrolled in remedial classes, teachers must determine if the remediation courses enhanced their reading comprehension, fluency, and reading proficiency. Teachers may acquire helpful information and techniques on how to do this through research conducted in other parts of the Philippines. It encourages teachers to reflect on and respond to their students' needs, fosters connections, and enhances student motivation and well-being, ultimately leading to improved learning outcomes.

Cluster VIII of the Schools Division Office of Urdaneta City stated that regularly assessing learners' reading performance levels can help identify their strengths and weaknesses. This assessment provides opportunities for targeted interventions that can assist students in overcoming reading difficulties and achieving better results (Duzon, K., & Paragas, J., 2023)

In Tarlac Province, programs such as the National Reading Program have played a crucial role in enhancing reading instruction for students. The program employs various methodologies to enhance fluency, comprehension, and overall performance, thus instilling in students a reading culture.

The National Reading Program is an integral component of the National Learning Camp, which is organized by the Department of Education. This dynamic platform facilitates the sharing of effective teaching practices and encourages educators to engage in various professional development opportunities, including workshops, seminars, and collaborative training sessions. Through these experiences, teachers can explore innovative methodologies tailored to meet the diverse needs of their students, ultimately enriching the educational landscape in Tarlac.

SME-AG Global School Inc., situated in the vibrant place in San Roque Bamban, Tarlac community, is a mid-sized private institution dedicated to delivering high-quality K-12 education. The school prides itself on educating a multicultural group of students, enrolling students from the surrounding communities.

SME-AG's educational philosophy emphasizes the importance of solid academic foundations, alongside values such as community commitment, personal growth, and social responsibility. The school strives to give its students a sense of belonging and respect for diversity.

The primary goal of SME-AG Global School Inc. is to enhance our school readiness mission, which empowers us to provide personalized instruction tailored to each student's unique needs. The school employs innovative, collaborative teaching methods that encourage critical thinking and creativity. In addition, the school is committed to fostering a supportive community and prioritizing the emotional and social well-being of its students, while maintaining a challenging academic program that encourages them to reach their full potential. Through the various programs and extracurricular initiatives, the school aims to develop well-rounded individuals who are academically prepared, responsible, and engaged members of society.

SME-AG Global School Inc. serves as an exemplary learning institution that has fully adopted the principles of the National Learning Camp. By incorporating phonics-based methods and various approaches to reading, including the Marungko approach, interactive reading materials, and shared reading, SME-AG Global School Inc. has created an engaging and dynamic learning environment for its students. The school emphasizes reading, particularly at the primary level, with elective courses such as Intensive Reading available. Intensive reading establishes foundational reading skills, including letter recognition, phonemic awareness, and vocabulary development. It develops fluency and understanding by repeated practice with materials appropriate for their age. It helps young learners

decode words, recognize sentence patterns, read stories, and develop reading habits. Additionally, it encourages early critical thinking and the ability to make connections between the text and their own experiences.

SME-AG Global School Inc. strongly emphasizes fostering a sense of belonging and participation through school events and partnerships with local organizations. The school also collaborates with Community Linkages to encourage reading at the primary level through an annual Off-Campus Outreach Reading Program. This activity is held during English Week and is in partnership with different public schools in Bamban, Tarlac. Primary-level students can present their reading skills through storytelling during this activity. Additionally, they can share and generously contribute whatever they can from their resources, benefiting the students at the partner public schools. The educators at SME-AG Global School Inc. have fully supported this initiative and encouraged diverse approaches to meet the students' needs.

Although the school offers elective subjects such as intensive reading and other reading programs, students still require additional attention and a more targeted approach to teaching reading. To monitor student progress in reading and comprehension, teachers at the school conduct a Quarterly Reading Assessment, which involves tracking the development of students' reading comprehension alongside giving input from parents and other stakeholders. This method helps the educator identify that some learners require intervention; while some students can thoroughly read the story and passages, they struggle to comprehend them. Some students struggle to identify the sounds of the alphabet and have difficulty reading words independently. By initiating this, the researcher aims to address the problem using a new approach and determine if it is suitable for improving their reading abilities and comprehension.

In addition, as a teacher, the researcher repeatedly encountered pupils in SME-AG Global School Inc. who knew how to read but struggled to understand the passages they were reading. This was evident in their inability to answer questions about the content of the stories they were reading. Learners were unable to discuss the story's gist or provide answers to the questions. Educators think that even though the school conducts a reading program, there are still students at risk in reading.

In this study, the researcher aimed to gauge the impact of the Fuller Approach on students' reading performance. To close this gap, further study is needed to investigate the benefits of the Fuller Approach on teaching pupils' reading performance in the SME-AG Global School Inc. setting. This research aims to evaluate the effectiveness of the Fuller approach in closing the reading performance gap at the primary level of SME-AG Global School Incorporated.

Statement of the Problem

This research evaluated the effectiveness of the Fuller Approach in enhancing the reading performance of Key Stage 1 learners at SME-AG Global School Inc. Reading performance can be developed and improved with practice, like any other skill. At an early age, children need to grow and develop throughout their early years by incorporating instructional aids and being immersed in reading-rich environments. Awareness of key developmental milestones in reading helps educators monitor children's progress and identify areas that may require additional support.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following:

1. How is the learners' reading performance described before employing the Fuller Approach?
2. How are the learners' reading performance described after employing the Fuller Approach?
3. Is there a significant difference between the learners' reading performance before and after employing the Fuller Approach?
4. What action plan is proposed to improve the learners' reading performance?

Null Hypothesis

There is no significant difference between learners' reading performance before and after employing the Fuller Approach.

Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

The present study was grounded in the theories of Progressivism and Constructivism, developed by Jean Piaget and Lev Vygotsky in the late 19th and early 20th centuries. This learning theory emphasizes how readers can actively construct meaning from the texts based on their prior knowledge, real-life experiences, and interactions with their environment. It also emphasizes the active role of learners in creating meaning and understanding of the world through interactions with the environment. Vygotsky's social-cultural theory emphasizes that learning is a social process that influences everyone's interaction, language, and culture. In reading instruction, learners can develop reading skills through **social interactions** and **scaffolding** provided by their teachers or peers. It helps learners reach higher reading levels through the support they may attain from their teachers and peers.

Constructivism is a key feature in research on the Fuller Approach to Key Stage 1 Reading Performance, providing a theory of meaning-making and active engagement. Additionally, this finding was consistent with research focusing on reading instruction and its utilization to enhance readers' reading performance. Constructivism also plays a central role in Fuller's approach to improving reading performance in Key Stage 1 learners. Rather than viewing them as passive recipients of knowledge, constructivism suggests that they actively build their understanding through experiences, prior knowledge, and social interactions.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of the Study

The above figure posited the conceptual framework of the study. It illustrates the survey flow, focusing on implementing the Fuller Approach to improve the performance of key stage 1 learners at SME-AG Global School Inc. The Independent variable is "Fuller Approach on Key Stage 1 learners," and the dependent variable is "learners' reading performance." The "Pretest" measures reading levels among pupils, which have six levels: Letter Level, Word Level, Paragraph Level, Story Level, Story + Comprehension Level, and Local Material Level. This research has investigated whether the Fuller Approach is practical and its impact on the reading performance of Key Stage 1 learners.

Other intervening variables include the implementation of the Fuller Approach, which assessed the impact on the reading performance of Key Stage 1 learners, and the recommended intervention plan, which gathered suggestions and feedback to enhance reading performance.

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2. METHODS

At the beginning of the study, a detailed explanation of the research process, participants' characteristics, and data collection instruments was given. Appropriate procedures were followed before the student was engaged in the research to ensure adherence to ethical standards and transparency. The class teacher, students, parents, and school principal were adequately informed of the study's aim, scope, and procedure. Informed consent was obtained from all the stakeholders to allow them to agree to be photographed throughout the research process. Such steps were necessary to maintain research ethical standards, protect participants' rights, and provide a suitable environment to produce genuine data.

Research Design

The study employed a quasi-experimental design with a one-group pretest-posttest design. In a one-group pretest and posttest design, the dependent variable was measured before and after the treatment was implemented. Like other research studies, they obtained the most reliable answers to their research questions by following the broader guidelines. The researcher employed a quasi-experimental research method, as the study focused on the Fuller Approach to Reading Performance for Key Stage 1 Learners. Quasi-experimental research characterizes and interprets what is and what is related to existing conditions of correspondence that occurred in prevalent practices, hopes, and procedures, as well as outcomes that are felt or developing changes.

To determine the key stages of learners' reading performance at SME-AG Global School Inc., the researcher administered the Functional Literacy Assessment Tool (FLAT) pretest, conducted a six-week intervention plan, and compared the results to the posttest outcomes.

Richard and Elizabeth Fuller developed the Fuller Approach. It integrates phonology and the alphabet with a comprehensive word recognition method for teaching (Eghbaria et al., 2022). Before using the fuller approach, learners must demonstrate mastery of the alphabet's names, sounds, and forms. The learners must also identify which letters are vowels and which are consonants. Moreover, this is the sequence of teaching the consonants. The first letter we teach in the Fuller approach is Mm, followed by Ss, Ll, Ff, Tt, and many more. When the teacher introduces the letter, they first show the words that begin with the target letter and then sound out each letter of the target. Next, they demonstrate how the target letter is formed, and finally, they provide an exercise to reinforce the formation of the target letter.

Furthermore, starting each lesson with a review of the letters, mastery of the lessons must be made fun in many ways that will surely capture the attention of young learners. Then, introduce the CVC words by families (those with similar endings), for instance, the -et family (get, jet, set, met, and so on). Pinpointing words with similar endings and those with rhyming endings helps them to read more effectively. Mastery of the family words can later be combined to form phrases, sentences, and possibly short stories. Introducing sight words like "are," "is," "the," "have," "on," and others can help children develop their reading skills. Another goal of this research is to enhance vocabulary. After implementing the Fuller approach, the posttest will occur after learners have completed the remediation program using the Fuller Approach. The impact of an intervention on a target population or the lack of a desired effect can be purposeful with a quasi-experimental strategy. The purpose of quasi-experimental methods is to investigate the causal relationships between a stimulus, intervention, or treatment and a study unit.

Research Locale

Figure 2. Location of SME-AG Global School Inc., Bambran, Tarlac

The study took place at SME-AG Global School, Inc. It was selected due to its reputation for academic excellence and commitment to educational innovation. SME-AG Global School Inc. has a track record of excellent instructional techniques and has demonstrated a readiness to investigate innovative methodologies to enhance student learning, particularly in the primary department's focus on improving literacy for all learners. This incremental method was consistent with the study's aims of investigating the efficacy of the Fuller approach in reading performance among key stage 1 learners.

Research Respondents

The participants were 17 learners from the rural area of Bambran, Tarlac, currently enrolled in grades 1 to 3 for the academic year 2024-2025. The study's respondents employed a one-group pretest and posttest design, which was selected because it aligns with the study's goals and objectives, as well as the specific requirements for participant inclusion. To determine the effectiveness of the interventions, all participants underwent a pretest using the Functional Literacy Assessment Tool (FLAT), a six-week intervention using the Fuller approach, and a post-test using the FLAT. A one-group pretest and posttest design was employed, where the dependent variable of a single group is measured before and after the intervention, allowing researchers to assess whether a change results from the intervention they conducted. According to Knapp T. R. (2016), the one-group pretest and posttest design has been widely criticized but continues to be used in different fields. It suggests various reasons for its continued use and gives some recommendations.

The researcher used the Functional Literacy Assessment Tool (FLAT) to assess the reading performance of Key Stage 1 learners at SME-AG Global School Inc. The data gathered were analyzed. It is the cornerstone of one-group pretest and posttest design as it minimizes bias and promotes representativeness. This process aims to define the respondents' reading performance clearly. Additionally, the six-week intervention program using the fuller approach will begin once the results are obtained. Furthermore, the researcher conducted the posttest after implementing the six-week intervention.

The use of a one-group pretest and posttest design can provide preliminary insights into the effectiveness of the intervention. The researcher must be transparent about their limitations and offer cautious recommendations. However, because the one-group pretest and posttest design provides a practical and feasible approach for obtaining preliminary insights into the potential effects of the intervention used, it is essential to acknowledge its limitations, particularly in the absence of a control group.

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A one-group pretest and posttest design has advantages and disadvantages like any other research design. For the advantages, it is often easier and more cost-effective to implement than the designs with the control group. It can also provide evidence of an intervention's potential effectiveness and permit further investigations with rigorous design. Additionally, it allows for observing changes within a single group over time, which can be valuable for understanding trends and issues in the education sector. For disadvantages, one group pretest and post-design might have the testing effect: taking the pretest itself might influence participant performance on the posttest.

Research Instrument

The Functional Literacy Assessment Tool (FLAT) serves as the baseline and research tool used in this study. FLAT is a standardized test of reading skills adopted from the Department of Education, and it will be utilized as a pre-test and post-test for the Key Stage 1 students enrolled in SME-AG Global School. The Functional Literacy Assessment Tool provides quantitative information on students' reading performance; therefore, it is possible to assess their performance before and after intervention. These research instruments will help evaluate the effectiveness of the Fuller Approach in enhancing key stage 1 reading performance.

Establishing a baseline of reading performance through the pretest by administering the Functional Literacy Assessment Tool (FLAT) to the key stages of one learner group enables a rigorous evaluation of the intervention's impact. Key Stage 1 learners will identify their reading level using the FLAT. The FLAT results were practically utilized to gather data on the respondents' level of reading performance in English. The Fuller Approach is the primary research material during the intervention period. The study can assess the Effectiveness of the Fuller Approach in facilitating measurable improvement in reading performance among the key stage 1 learners. The goal is to improve the reading performance of the participants. A posttest will be administered after a six-week intervention to measure the improvement in student reading performance. The scores on the posttest enable researchers to determine whether the intervention is producing differences in reading performance.

Additionally, with quantitative data from the FLAT, there is an opportunity to analyze students' reading proficiency systematically. Standardization of the test ensures the result is objective and can be compared across participants, making the result more reliable. By assessing learners' reading performance before and after the intervention, the study can establish patterns, trends, and differences in learning outcomes, thereby gaining valuable insights into the effectiveness of the Fuller Approach.

The FLAT is an effective tool that develops literacy and facilitates the shift in English reading achievement. It monitors students' progress and defines targeted intervention areas for at-risk and below-grade readers. Teachers can immediately utilize this measuring instrument, as it enables them to classify reading levels simultaneously, pinpoint struggling readers, and make it a valuable tool for developing students' reading performance. It can also effectively tailor instructional strategies to address individual learning needs by disaggregating assessment data based on specific reading performance. This personalized approach to reading instruction aligns with the study's objectives and underscores the research instrument's practical utility in informing evidence-based teaching practices.

The Functional Literacy Assessment Tool measures an individual's ability to apply in reading. This assessment extends beyond basic literacy (the ability to read and write) to determine how well a person can read and identify areas for improvement.

Data Gathering Procedure

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The data-gathering procedure in this study employed a quasi-experimental design, featuring a one-group pretest and posttest to ensure a comprehensive approach to both quantitative and qualitative data collection. This process took place over several weeks, starting with the pretest and review, and ending with the implementation of the Fuller Approach as the reading intervention.

The following documents were submitted for review and approval in accordance with DepEd's Regional Memorandum (RM 228, s. 2020). The researcher provided a formal letter of intent and instrument for the study, followed by a letter of endorsement from the university, a copy of the approved clearance from the University Research Ethics Review Committee, and Informed consent forms (for all participants, including assent letters for those under 18 years of age).

The researcher sought formal permission from the School Owner and Principal of SME-AG Global School to ensure the study was conducted within ethical and legal guidelines. It involved submitting an official request to the School Owner and Principal to conduct the study on the Key Stage 1 learners at SME-AG Global School. The request was accompanied by necessary documentation, including a letter of endorsement from the researcher's university, proof of ethical clearance from the University Research Ethics Review Committee, and relevant consent forms for all participants.

Upon receiving approval from the School Principal, the researcher obtained parental consent to notify parents that their children were used as study participants. Additionally, the researcher adheres to the appropriate ethical guidelines while conducting the study. After obtaining the parents' consent, the researcher began preparing her plan for implementing the study. The researcher communicated with the subject teacher of grade 3 and conducted an orientation on administering the Functional Literacy Assessment Tool (FLAT). The subject teacher of Grade 3 and the researcher, who handles Grades 1 and 2, began administering the pretest to the Key Stage 1 learners to assess their reading performance. The pretest of FLAT established the baseline of the learner's reading performance. After getting the results of the FLAT (pretest), the researcher determined the learners' reading performance. Once determined, the researcher develops a six-week program intervention using the Fuller Approach, which was already administered to the Key Stage 1 learners. The researcher documented everything during the interaction between the researcher and the subject teacher with the students.

The interactions and engagement of Key Stage 1 learners were observed, recorded, and documented. Subsequently, the posttest was administered using the Functional Literacy Assessment Tool, which served as the study's baseline. Moreover, the posttest findings were tallied and analyzed using the required statistical treatment. The posttest assesses the implementation of the Fuller Approach in the reading performance by comparing the pretest and posttest results. Lastly, the Effectiveness of the Fuller Approach on reading performance can be evaluated.

Additionally, documentation and observation were carried out throughout the intervention period. Observing the implementation of the Fuller Approach and documenting the instructional strategies, student involvement, and difficulties that participants encountered are all part of this qualitative data-gathering strategy. These observations provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of the strategy.

Implementing the Fuller Approach enables learners to systematically develop their reading performance skills through structured activities and assessments aligned with the intervention program. Maintaining an encouraging and supportive learning environment throughout the program is crucial for motivating learners and helping them achieve success in reading.

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Program of Activities for Grade 1 learners

WEEK	Date	Activity	Assessment
1	February 17-21, 2025	8:00-8:30---Motivational Activity 8:30-10:30 --- Implementation of the FLAT pretest to Grade 1 students.	Oral Assessment
2	February 24-28, 2025	8:00-8:30---Motivational Activity 8:00-10:00 Fuller Approach Implementation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review/teach the sounds and shapes of the alphabet • Introduce pictures that begin with the target sound (vocabulary building) • Practice activity (if needed) • Rereading 	Oral Reading Practice
3	March 3-7, 2025	8:00-8:30 ---Motivational Activity 8:00-10:00 Fuller Approach Implementation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Word families (CVC medial a and e), phrases and sentences, and short stories • Practice Activity • Rereading 	Oral Reading Practice
4	March 10-14, 2025	8:00-8:30 ---Motivational Activity 8:00-10:00 Fuller Approach Implementation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Word families (CVC medial i and o), phrases and sentences, and short stories • Practice Activity • Rereading 	Oral Reading Practice
5	March 17-21, 2025	8:00-8:30 ---Motivational Activity 8:00-10:00 Fuller Approach Implementation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Word families (CVC medial u and long sounds), phrases and sentences, and short stories • Practice Activity • Rereading 	Oral Reading Practice
6	March 24-28, 2025	8:00-8:30 ---Motivational Activity 8:30-10:30--- Implementation of FLAT posttest to Grade 1 students.	Oral Reading/Paper and Pencil Assessment

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Program of Activities for Grade 2 learners

WEEK	Date	Activity	Assessment
1	February 17-21, 2025	8:00-8:30 ---Motivational Activity 8:30-10:30 --- Implementation of the FLAT pretest to Grade 2 students.	Oral Assessment
2	February 24-28, 2025	8:00-8:30 ---Motivational Activity 8:00-10:00 Fuller Approach Implementation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review the sounds and shapes of the alphabet • Introduce pictures that begin with the target sound (vocabulary building) • Practice activity (if needed) • Rereading 	Oral Reading Practice
3	March 3-7, 2025	8:00-8:30 ---Motivational Activity 8:00-10:00 Fuller Approach Implementation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Word families (CVC medial a and e, i), phrases and sentences, and short stories • Practice Activity • Rereading 	Oral Reading Practice
4	March 10-14, 2025	8:00-8:30 ---Motivational Activity 8:00-10:00 Fuller Approach Implementation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Word families (CVC medial o and u), phrases and sentences, and short stories • Sight words and long a sounds • Practice Activity • Rereading 	Oral Reading Practice
5	March 17-21, 2025	8:00-8:30 ---Motivational Activity 8:00-10:00 Fuller Approach Implementation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stories with comprehension questions • Practice Activity • Rereading 	Oral Reading Practice
6	March 24-28, 2025	8:00-8:30 ---Motivational Activity 8:30-10:30--- Implementation of FLAT posttest to Grade 2 learners.	Oral Reading/Paper and Pencil Assessment

Program of Activities for Grade 3 learners

WEEK	Date	Activity	Assessment
1	February 17-21, 2025	8:00-8:30 ---Motivational Activity 8:30-10:30 --- Implementation of the FLAT pretest to Grade 2 students.	Oral Assessment
2	February 24-28, 2025	8:00-8:30 ---Motivational Activity 8:00-10:00 Fuller Approach Implementation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Review the sounds and shapes of the alphabet Introduce pictures that begin with the target sound (vocabulary building) Review word families (cvc medial A- U) Practice activity (if needed) Rereading 	Oral Reading Practice
3	March 3-7, 2025	8:00-8:30 ---Motivational Activity 8:00-10:00 Fuller Approach Implementation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sight words and long a sounds Stories with comprehension Practice Activity Rereading 	Oral Reading Practice
4	March 10-14, 2025	8:00-8:30 ---Motivational Activity 8:00-10:00 Fuller Approach Implementation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stories with comprehension questions Practice Activity Rereading 	Oral Reading Practice
5	March 17-21, 2025	8:00-8:30 ---Motivational Activity 8:00-10:00 Fuller Approach Implementation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stories with comprehension questions Practice Activity Rereading 	Oral Reading Practice
6	March 24-28, 2025	8:00-8:30 ---Motivational Activity 8:30-10:30--- Implementation of FLAT posttest to Grade 3 learners	Oral Reading/Paper and Pencil Assessment

Before the pretest was administered, a teacher's orientation was conducted to provide knowledge, discuss the tools to be used, and explain how to implement them, thereby giving teachers the preparation and confidence they needed to deliver the pretest and intervention program effectively. Teachers implemented the reading intervention over six weeks. Students participated in activities designed to improve their reading performance during this time. The principal observed the classes while the reading intervention was being implemented. These observations focused on the student's engagement, the teacher's facilitation, and student responses to the Intervention reading program.

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After implementing the Fuller Approach, a posttest was conducted to assess their reading performance using the Functional Literacy Assessment tool. It involved collecting data to evaluate the effectiveness and quality of the materials.

Data Analysis

The T-test Dependent sample formula was used in this research to examine the significant difference in reading performance and comprehension between the research participants on their pretest and posttest after receiving the Fuller Approach as reading intervention materials. The researchers measured the group's mean performance in both the pretest and the posttest. Then, the mean score difference between the pretest and the posttest will be interpreted using a T-test for a Dependent sample. The significance level will be set at 0.05. The researchers used a T-Test with a Dependent sample in this study.

$$t = \frac{\sum D}{\sqrt{\frac{n \sum D^2 - (\sum D)^2}{n-1}}}$$

Formula:

Legends:

t = t-test

$\sum D$ is the sum of the differences between the paired observations

$\sum D^2$ = sum of squared differences

n = number of paired observations

Degree of Freedom (df) = n-1

The researcher developed a mechanism, which the expert validated. The researcher used FLAT rubrics to obtain the T-test scores for the pretest and posttest among the key Stage 1 learners. These rubrics assessed the reading performance of Key Stage 1 learners and how far they can progress. When the child reaches the paragraph level and the researcher determines that they can no longer progress to the next level, the examiner will stop and collect the scores obtained. The students cannot continue if they do not meet the requirements outlined in the Functional Literacy Assessment Tool.

FLAT RATING SCALE			
Reading Level	Description of Levels	Scores	Remarks
Letter Level	Can read letters	10/10	1 point per identify letters
Word Level	Can read common words	10/10	1 point per identify words
Paragraph Level	Can read paragraph	5/5	1 point- cannot read the word
			2 points- 3 or more mistakes
			3 points- 2 mistakes only
			4 points- 1 mistake only
			5 points- NO mistake
Story Level	Can read story	5/5	1 point- cannot read the story
			2 points- 3 or more mistakes
			3 points- 2 mistakes only
			4 points- 1 mistake only
			5 points- NO mistake
Story + Comprehension Level	Can read and understand story	5/5	*5 points for the story*
			1 point- cannot read the story
			2 points- 3 or more mistakes
			3 points- 2 mistakes only
			4 points- 1 mistake only
Local Material and Comprehension Level	Can read and understand Local material	5/5	5 points for the local material
			1 point- cannot read the story
			2 points- 3 or more mistakes
			3 points- 2 mistakes only
			4 points- 1 mistake only
Total Scores		5/5	5 points for comprehension questions (Total of 5 questions)
		50/50	

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter followed the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data in the sequence described in the issue description. The present research aimed to evaluate the impact of the Fuller Approach for SME-AG Global School Inc. by applying the Fuller Approach method in teaching reading to the Key Stage 1 students.

3.1 Learners' Reading Performance Before Employing the Fuller Approach

A pretest was administered to assess the respondents' initial reading performance, and the test was described based on the FLAT as the primary instrument used to determine their reading performance level. It served as the study's baseline for employing the appropriate intervention programs. The Functional Literacy Assessment Tool (FLAT) determines the reading performance level of Key Stage 1 learners. Following the pretest, the Key Stage 1 learners participate in the Fuller Approach as a reading intervention, which involves reviewing and rereading to enhance reading performance. The Fuller Approach fostered an in-depth approach to engaging in reading activities for learning. Instead of learners being passive readers, it encourages more profound engagement with the word, making reading more enjoyable and meaningful for them.

The Functional Literacy Assessment Tool levels are as follows: Letter Level, Word Level, Paragraph Level, Story Level, Story + Comprehension Level, and Local Material + Comprehension Level. The discussions are presented in the following presentation.

Table 1 below indicates the reading performance of the Key Stage 1 learners after the pretest. Some learners struggle to read words at the paragraph level.

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Table 1. FLAT Pretest Results

Grade Level	Letter Level	Word Level	Paragraph Level	Story Level	Story + Comprehension Level	Local Material Level
Grade 1	0	3	2	1	0	0
Grade 2	0	2	2	2	0	0
Grade 3	0	0	2	2	1	0
Total	0	5	6	5	1	0

Of the 17 learners in Key Stage 1 who participated in the study, the pretest revealed that 5 were at the Word Level, 6 were at the Paragraph Level, 5 were at the Story Level, and 1 was at the Story + Comprehension Level. The overall results are broken down by grade level as follows: On the Grade 1 level, there are 3 on the Word Level, 2 on the Paragraph Level, and 1 on the Story Level; on the Grade 2 Level, there are 2 on the Word Level, 2 on the Paragraph Level, and 2 on the Story Level. On the Grade 3 Level, there are 2 on the Paragraph Level, 2 on the Story Level, and 1 on the Story + Comprehension Level.

Furthermore, this indicates that learners are achieving lower scores in relation to their grade level, highlighting the need for reading enhancement. Studies suggest that interventions for reading problems and attempts to address these issues should begin at the primary level of education (Akyol & Boyaci-Altinay, 2019). Today, the primary purpose of reading is to make sense of what is read (Gedik & Akyol, 2022). It is worth noting that no one from the group of learners has reached the Letter Level; therefore, there are still learners whose reading performance remains at the word level, indicating a need for intervention.

Continuous monitoring and assessment of learners' reading performance should be an integral part of the educational strategy to track improvements and make necessary adjustments. Applying the Fuller Approach is designed to enhance reading performance using the English alphabet. It also emphasizes the importance of reviewing phonemic awareness, a crucial component for reading success. An effective way to improve learners' reading performance in the beginning reading stage is also crucial for developing macro skills in reading, resulting in solid comprehension skills that are essential for learners' overall reading performance.

According to a study by Gedik and Akyol (2022), teachers should not overlook the crucial component of reading fluency to enhance reading performance. They should, therefore, incorporate reading activities into their classrooms to develop fluent reading skills. Researchers, on the other hand, have conducted similar studies on reading difficulties, highlighting problems in reading that cause learners to experience difficulties.

In conclusion, the analysis of the pretest results suggests a significant need for intervention programs to enhance the reading performance of Key Stage 1 learners, particularly those who are struggling to keep up. It provides a valuable baseline for developing and implementing an effective way to improve reading performance.

3.2 Learners' Reading Performance After Employing the Fuller Approach

The Fuller Approach was employed as the primary reading intervention in the study. After implementing the Fuller Approach, a post-test was administered to determine the reading performance or level of the learners based on their reading level, using the Functional Literacy Assessment Tool (FLAT) as the instrument. The discussion is presented in the following presentations.

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Table 2 below presents the reading performance of Key Stage 1 learners as described after implementing the Fuller Approach (posttest).

Table 2. FLAT Posttest Results

Grade Level	Letter Level	Word Level	Paragraph Level	Story Level	Story + Comprehension Level	Local Material Level
Grade 1	0	0	0	4	2	0
Grade 2	0	0	0	2	4	0
Grade 3	0	0	0	1	3	1
Total	0	0	0	7	9	1

The table above displays the reading performance of the Key Stage 1 learners in the posttest. It revealed that among the 17 participants from grades 1 to 3, scores of 26-46 were achieved on the story and local material levels, indicating that learners have progressed in their reading performance. Grade levels break down the overall results: on the Grade 1 Level, there are 4 on the story level and 2 on the story + comprehension Level; on the Grade 2 level, there are 2 on the Story Level and 4 on the Story + Comprehension Level; on the Grade 3 Level, there is 1 on the Story Level, 3 on the Story + Comprehension Level, and 1 on the Local Material Level.

According to the FLAT instrument post-test results, all learners showed improvement in their reading performance. The fuller approach material helps improve the reading levels of the Key Stage 1 learners. It implies that the learning support materials given as interventions to the learners are effective. Reading is one of the four skills that should be learned before listening, writing, and speaking. Idulog et al. (2023) stated that it is a prerequisite for all learning areas, enabling every learner to acquire knowledge in various subjects. This is because if an individual has difficulties with reading, they are likely to struggle with other subjects as well. Studies have shown that targeted reading interventions can significantly improve reading assessment performance.

Additionally, over the course of six weeks, implementing the Fuller approach to teaching reading to Key Stage 1 learners proved to be an effective intervention in enhancing their reading performance. Embracing this approach enhances retention and enables learners to grasp complex concepts more effectively.

Furthermore, it is typical to observe a moderate range of improvement in results when assessing the effectiveness of the Fuller Approach in reading performance. One of the practical components of the intervention was rereading the Fuller Approach. The teacher implemented a personalized approach, working one-on-one with each learner to address their specific reading needs. The one-on-one interaction between the teacher and the learners made them realize that each learner has their own reading needs, and it targeted scaffolding and instruction that led to substantial progress in the learners' reading performance.

By integrating the rereading in the fuller approach, learners experience significant growth in their reading performance. This study demonstrates an important enhancement compared to their pretest. It indicates positive improvements resulting from the reading intervention and practice. A deeper engagement of learners in reading allows them to grasp the nuances of words effectively. By fostering a habit of deep rereading, learners become more discerning consumers of information. Furthermore, this approach enriches vocabulary, enhances communication skills, and cultivates a lifelong appreciation for reading. A recent study highlights that supplementary reading materials

provided to learners, combined with teachers' commitment and patience in teaching reading, have a significant impact on learners' reading performance (Meramonte, 2022).

3.3 Significant Difference between the Pretest and Posttest Results of the Key Stage 1 learners' Reading Performance

This study used a T-test to examine the significant differences between the pretest and posttest results for the 17 key stage 1 learners. The analysis examined whether the intervention resulted in statistically significant improvements in reading performance, thereby indicating its effectiveness.

The table below illustrates the significant difference between the key stage 1 learners' pre-test and post-test scores.

Table 3. Test of Significant Difference Between the Pretest and Posttest Results Of the Key Stage 1 Learners' Reading Performance

Variable	Mean	df	t-cri	t-stat	Decision	Remark
Pretest	-9.882	16	1.745	-10.152	Reject the Null Hypothesis	Significant
Posttest						

The table above presents the significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores for the 17 participants, as determined by a t-test, which yielded a value of -9.882. The degrees of freedom are 16, with a t-stat of -10.152 and a critical value of 1.745 taken before and after the reading intervention program, showing an increase in scores. This difference is significant because the null hypothesis is rejected, $t(16) = -10.152, p < 0.01, < 0.05$. In other words, the reading intervention program, also known as the Fuller Approach, improved students' test scores in Key Stage 1. The results indicated a significant difference between the pretest and posttest

The analysis reveals that the Fuller Approach reading intervention program has a significant and positive impact on students' reading performance in Key Stage 1. These findings demonstrate the effectiveness of the intervention in enhancing learners' reading performance.

3.4 Proposed Action Plan for Key Stage 1 Learners' Reading Performance.

The Proposed Action Plan for the reading performance of Key Stage 1 learners at SME-AG Global School will focus on improving learners' reading performance and further enhancing the Effectiveness of the Fuller Approach.

Areas of Concern	Strategy	Activity	Mean of Verification
Learners have limited Word knowledge and difficulty in understanding word meanings in a story.	Utilizing word meanings in a story involves pre-teaching key vocabulary through visuals and context clues to support comprehension during reading and engage students actively. Invite an experienced	Reading Comprehension Workshop: Conduct a series of workshops that help students in reading comprehension, including building the basics, Vocabulary in context, making inferences, summarizing, and connecting.	Participant Vocabulary log Worksheet and Exit slip to measure their understanding.

	reading teacher to share their expertise and teach students.		
Learners Reading Comprehension	Teachers will implement effective strategies to help learners make inferences, draw conclusions, summarize, synthesize, and connect stories read. They will use guided reading questions and graphic organizers (such as story maps or thinking webs) to actively support comprehension and critical thinking before, during, and after reading.	Conducting activities such as using story maps to help learners organize key story elements, make connections, and synthesize ideas. Guide students through comprehension questions before, during, and after reading to support inference-making, drawing conclusions, and summarizing.	Reflection journal and summarization of paragraphs/stories evaluated by the facilitator using a rubric that assesses the extent of the experience gained.
Learners' level of competence in reading	The learners' level of competence in reading can be enhanced through targeted strategies that develop comprehension skills, vocabulary, and critical thinking during reading activities.	Activities that support this include guided reading sessions with comprehension questions, vocabulary-building games, and the use of graphic organizers to help learners analyze and reflect on texts. These activities encourage active engagement and strengthen their understanding and interpretation of what they read.	Reading comprehension assessments, vocabulary quizzes, completed graphic organizers, student reading journals, and teacher observation checklists that track progress in making inferences, summarizing, and connecting ideas from texts

This document presents a detailed three-day Reading Comprehension Project Proposal designed to enhance students' reading proficiency. It articulates clear objectives, outlines methodical approaches, and anticipates specific outcomes, thereby establishing a robust framework for implementation.

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Furthermore, the proposal includes a collection of targeted assessment tools designed to evaluate the effectiveness of the intervention. These instruments will help identify learners' strengths and areas for improvement, enabling the tailoring of instructional strategies to meet individual needs and enhance overall reading performance effectively.

PROJECT PROPOSAL

Title : **UNLOCKING MEANING: A THREE-DAY READING COMPREHENSION WORKSHOP**

Proponent : **REVILEN S. VERANO**

Objectives :

- ✓ Enhance students' ability to understand, interpret, and analyse written texts.
- ✓ Introduce and apply effective reading comprehension strategies.
- ✓ Promote critical thinking and independent reading skills in a short-term, intensive format.
- ✓ **Use comprehension strategies** such as predicting, summarising, questioning, and making inferences.
- ✓ **Expand vocabulary and context clue usage** to improve overall reading fluency and understanding.
- ✓ Demonstrate improved reading comprehension through guided and independent reading tasks, including group discussions and written responses.

Introduction

Reading comprehension is a vital skill for academic success and lifelong learning. It involves more than decoding words—it requires understanding, interpreting, and engaging with text. Nevertheless, many students struggle due to limited vocabulary and a lack of effective strategies.

The three-day workshop, "**Unlocking Meaning**," aims to equip students with essential reading strategies through interactive activities and collaborative learning. It focuses on developing skills such as identifying key ideas, making inferences, and thinking critically. In today's information-rich world, strong comprehension skills are crucial. This workshop provides students with the tools they need to read with confidence, understanding, and purpose.

Rationale

Reading comprehension is essential for academic success across all subjects, yet many students struggle due to limited vocabulary, weak background knowledge, and ineffective strategies. These challenges can lead to poor performance and a lack of confidence in reading.

This three-day workshop offers a focused intervention to help learners enhance key comprehension skills, including identifying main ideas, making inferences, and utilizing context clues. Through interactive activities and collaborative learning, students gain practical tools to better understand and engage with texts.

The program's short duration makes it suitable for schools that need quick, targeted support. Beyond improving literacy, the workshop fosters critical thinking and builds a foundation for lifelong learning.

Procedure

The workshops will be structured as follows:

Time	Activity	Strategy	Participants	Mean of Verification
8:00-12:00 am	Day 1: Building the Basics: Activating Prior Knowledge and Setting the Purpose	Interactive lectures, group assessment, and discussion	Students	Exit slip: "One thing I already knew + one thing I want to learn"
1:00-4:00 pm	Day 1: Vocabulary in Context	Guided Practice, independent practice, and Reinforcement activities	Students	Vocabulary log entries (word + meaning + strategy used)
8:00-12:00 am	Day 2: Identifying the Main Idea and Supporting Details in a Story	Main Idea Sorting and story maps fill in	Students	Complete main idea/detail graphic organizer
1:00-4:00 pm	Day 2: Summarizing, Synthesizing, and Connecting	Summarising main points, Synthesising, and making meaningful text connections	Students	Summarisation paragraph/stories graded by rubric
8:00-12:00 am	Day 3: Making Inferences and Drawing Conclusions	Inferring and drawing logical conclusions	Students	Reflection journal: "What helped you infer today?"
1:00-4:00 pm	Day 3: Reflection on Text Reading	think beyond the words by analyzing, evaluating, and connecting the text to their own experiences,	Students	Class Discussions or Sharing Sessions

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Budgetary Requirement

The budgetary requirements for the 3-day Reading Comprehension Workshops will be covered by the students through a registration fee of **₱ 550** per participant. Given that the school administration will provide the venue for the workshop at no cost, this support significantly reduces the overall financial burden.

Estimate of 17 participants: Total budget **PHP 9350**

Materials	Quantity	Price per unit	Total
Resource Speakers	3	1500	4500
Refreshments (AM and PM Snacks)	27	80 per pax	2160
Lunch (for 3 speakers and participating faculty)	10 pax per day	200 per pax	2000
Contingency Fund		690	
Total		9350	

Proposed by:
REVILEN S. VERANO
 FACILITATOR

Approved by:
ELMER S. DUNGCA
 SCHOOL PRINCIPAL

PROJECT PROPOSAL

Title : UNLOCKING MEANING: A THREE-DAY READING COMPREHENSION WORKSHOP

EXIT SLIP	
One thing I already knew	One thing I want to learn
ANSWER:	ANSWER:

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COMPREHENSION WORKSHOP**

VOCABULARY LOG ENTRIES

READING		
WORD & SPELLING	DEFINITION & WORD CLASS	SENTENCE

**Title : UNLOCKING MEANING: A THREE-DAY READING
COMPREHENSION WORKSHOP**

REFLECTION JOURNAL

NAME:
WHAT HELPED YOU INFER TODAY?
ANSWER:

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SUMMARIZING RUBRIC

Criteria	Advanced (10)	Proficient (8)	Partially Proficient (7)	Average (5)	Emergent (3)	Score
I began by telling the title of the story and the main idea.						
I use transition words to organize my summary.						
I retell the beginning of the story.						
I retell the middle of the story.						
I retell the end of the story.						
I restate the main idea at the end of my summary.						
States a chronological sequence of events from a story.						
Identifies details that support the main idea.						
Identifies causes for events or situations.						
Combine text clues with their own knowledge and experience to reach a new understanding.						
Total Score						

**EVALUATED:
Revilen S. Verano**

4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

After thoroughly analyzing the data from the six-week reading intervention program for Key Stage 1 Learners, the following conclusions were drawn.

1. Most key stage 1 learners in SME-AG Global School are categorized by reading level at the word and paragraph levels (pretest).
2. The posttest results for the reading performance of key stage 1 learners showed improvement in both story level and comprehension, demonstrating significant progress. It shows that students are now ready to meet a grade-level standard in reading performance.
3. A significant difference between the pretest and posttest indicates the success of the fuller method of reading texts.
4. To improve their reading performance, targeted interventions in paragraphs, story reading, rhyme, and phonological awareness are suggested learning experiences for Key Stage 1 students. Differentiation teaching, daily reading, monitoring for reading, and establishing a whole and interactive learning environment are also suggested learning experiences.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion of the study, the researcher offered the following recommendations;

1. The key Stage 1 learners should utilize the proposed action plan.
2. Teachers should teach and build strong phonemic awareness in the students.
3. Encourage other teachers to provide intervention materials to improve the learners' reading performance.
4. Conduct Quarterly Assessments and provide feedback to monitor students' progress, ensuring individualized support and areas for improvement in reading performance.

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